

PEUTRANSP Policy Brief N. 1

Individual Researchers and the European Parliament: Informal Networks, Transparency, and Breaking the “Brussels Bubble” *

Colleen Boland

University of Radboud, Nijmegen, Netherlands

Executive Summary

What do we know about the informal interchanges between individual researchers and the European Parliament (EP)? This brief on the EP and informal networks with researchers first provides a short overview of the actors involved in the links between the two, within the context of study on the research-policy nexus and the EP to date. In doing so, it makes a distinction between formal and informal processes. It then proceeds to evidence a small case study of Dutch researchers in the field of migration studies and Dutch MEPs gathering information on the topic of migration to illustrate the less visible and understudied topic of informal exchange between the EP and researchers.

Based on this case study, the reflection ultimately points to the influential role of brokers of research and policy in Brussels, the lack of knowledge and visibility into informal interactions between researchers and the EP, and the possibility that a select group of researchers across Europe engaging with the EP could be expanded in order to improve

* This study has been elaborated in the framework of the research project “Legislative Transparency in the European Parliament”, funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities, 2024-2027 (Ref. PID2022-136330NB-I00).

evidence-based policy. It argues for a series of policy takeaways: are the current rules (and formal mechanisms) insufficient to hold the EP and researchers transparent and accountable, or would further regulation and bureaucracy stifle exchange and efficient policymaking? What can be done to encourage those individual researchers outside of the “Brussels bubble” to offer their expertise to the EP, thus facilitating diverse and comprehensive evidence-based policy? Finally, how do various research disciplines interact more, less or differently with varying agendas in the EP, and what does this mean for the degree of evidence-based policy?

Background

Ample literature addresses lobbying and interest groups as relates to EU governance (Bunea 2018 and 2019; Coman, 2019; Boucher and Hobbs, 2014; Sherrington, 2000; Ullrich, 2004). Work of to date often investigates the role of NGOs and think tanks; it can focus on comparative differences between Brussels and Washington (Rastrick, 2017), the organizational functioning of think tanks themselves in securing reputation and funding (Perez, 2014), or the relationship between think tanks and the European Commission (Boswell, 2008). However, there is still room to further understand and map how research connects or mutually interacts with European Parliament (EP) policy—in particularly informally. Relatedly, recent work has investigated groups’ access to EP policy-making processes (Coen and Katsaitis, 2019; Marshall, 2010; Rasmussen, 2015), MEPs’ recognition of interest groups (Ibenskas and Bunea, 2020), and MEPs’ transparency behaviour regarding their contacts with interest representatives (Font and Ares, 2025; Font and Pérez-Durán, 2023). However, there are scarce insights on the individual researchers or “experts” and informal mechanisms and processes behind the scenes. This brief inquires as to the ways in which individual researchers connect informally with the EP’s work, to what extent this is visible or significant, and whether further understanding or monitoring of these channels would impact EP expertise and efficacy.

Actors involved in research-policy nexus

The EP requires expert and technical expertise to assess and amend the Commission's legislative proposals and negotiate with the Council. There are various interest groups, civil society organizations (CSOs) and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), academics, think tanks, public officials, and miscellaneous external actors informing this parliamentary expertise (Elomäki and Haapala, 2024). While this piece is trying to better understand the influence or role of individual researchers, the role of think tanks and advocacy organizations is important to understand as well, given that they often act as mediators.

There are various think tanks and advocacy organizations informing EU policy and institutions like the EP. Arguably, some are substantially more influential, and how these organisations broker relationships between actors remains complex or behind the scenes (Abelson, 2016). Think tanks and researchers do not just “inform” the EU parliamentarian, but policy impact is “multi-dimensional” in that it can contribute to ideas and frameworks, how data is constructed, gathered and disseminated, and in creating awareness (Stone and Ullrich, 2003). While many think tanks and researchers declare themselves independent and impartial, their work is often at least partially funded by EU institutions like the Commission.

Formal mechanisms in place mediating EP relationships with individual researchers

The EP also has its own in-house think tank and research institution established in 2013, The European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS), with the aim of providing “comprehensive research and analytical support to the MEPs, its parliamentary committees and the EP as a whole” and “independent, objective and authoritative information” (European Parliament, 2024). The EPRS may commission or contract think tanks and research institutes if their own in-house expertise or capacity is not sufficient for the topic, and these organizations may then in turn also reach out to individual researchers (CEPS, 2024).

Particularly in relationship with the EPRS, the EP can more formally request expertise. Otherwise, academic experts could be invited to committee hearings, which serve as a key important formal channel; MEPs, parties within the Parliament or committees can commission studies as well (Elomäki and Haapala, 2024). Formal processes could be considered as monitored via the transparency register, which was agreed upon by the EP, the Council of the European Union and the European Commission as a joint register in 2021 (2024b). Interest groups that “carry out activities to influence the EU policy and decision-making process” are obliged to register here (European Union, 2024a). Figure 1 summarizes the percentage of interest organizations entered in the Transparency Register, by categories. Among those organizations directly or indirectly dealing with research functions, professional consultancies represent 28% of the entities, whereas research institutions represent 3.6% and academic institutions just represent 0.02%.

Figure 1. Interest organisations entered in the Transparency Register

Source: EU Transparency Register (2024)

As regards research institutions, you can find in the register the Centre for European Policy Studies and the European Policy Centre, Brussels-based EU think tanks that collaborate with independent researchers in addition to employing their own staff and being commissioned to write reports for institutions like the EPRS. Relevant categories in this discussion include

academic institutions, professional consultancies and think tanks and research institutions. However, as of this writing and a search of the register, individual outside researchers with whom they collaborate are not available, and according to the guidelines on the website, do not seem to be required to register (European Union, 2024a).

It should be noted that there is continuous mobility between staff of EU institutions, and the civil servants changing roles between different EU institutions may also have experience as professionals from other organizations or vice versa (Georgakakis and Rowell, 2013). This can explain how the EPRS, for example, builds relationships with outside researchers, or how parliamentarians or their staff may approach an individual researcher for expertise.

The migration studies example: independent researcher and MEP perspectives

Exploring these dynamics in the field of migration studies (and migration policy) was selected for the case study because EU competences in migration and asylum have been expanding, which perhaps demands more engagement between academic experts and the EPRS than in other policy fields (Lavanex, 2016). Moreover, the increasing visibility of the topic in Member States throughout Europe and its salience in recent election campaigns renders it a relevant example (Fix, 2024; Font, 2025). This is particularly the case in the Dutch context, with a change in government heralding a migration policy overhaul (Mak et al., 2024). Finally, there are many established migration and asylum NGOs and think tanks engaging with more formal mechanisms influencing EP policy, which can also serve as mediators for informal networks.

To flesh out the dynamics of informal exchange between individual researchers and MEPs, and also to identify gaps in current research, expert interviews in the Dutch case study context were conducted with two migration studies academics who have contributed to parliamentary expertise, and with two MEPs from the Green Party, to gain perspectives from both sides. Interviews were held virtually and not recorded, and informed consent and information sheets for verbal consent provided.

1. Researcher viewpoints

In the interviews, researchers reported were asked as to their experience with formal and informal channels to the EP. Formal channels included being approached to write reports or appear before committees, as well as being asked to provide research for the EPRS, or for studies commissioned by the EPRS by think tanks like the Centre for European Policy Studies (CEPS, 2024). Relatedly, they pointed out if there is a contract of less than 15,000 euro, there is no need to tender publicly and contracts can go through a negotiated procedure, i.e., an EP committee could choose an intended or desired researcher for the job (European Council, 2024).

As for the topic of this brief, the indirect or informal interactions these independent academics reported included: being asked to contribute to reports by advocacy organizations; colleagues from an EP party would ask off the record for advice; staff of an MEP would reach out to informally discuss issues with them after having already established a relationship in Brussels; or, they would take the initiative to engage in informal conversation, or to offer MEPs a report or policy brief they had been working on. As part of this, they noted that being visible or present at events in Brussels were key in leading to both formal and informal interactions with the EP. This reflects other studies that notes a very Brussels-specific group of experts that can more frequently interact with MEPs (Elomäki and Haapala, 2024). Their observations also demonstrate the two-way nature of exchange.

A key takeaway included their hypothesis that the more think tanks, research institutions or even individual academic knowledge exchange available to the EP (i.e., more channels of both expert and technical expertise), the greater the probability of quality and objective advice and evidence for the EP. This way, rather than just being relationship-based, with several actors “competing” in this playing field of experts, the likelihood of being solicited by the EP for further support would be increased or secured again based on the integrity, relevance and quality of past advice.

2. MEP viewpoints

MEPs offered their insight into how they work with researchers both formally and informally. They confirmed the observations made by the researchers as to the two-way nature of exchange. They also overviewed their formal engagement with individual researchers, but the key insights as to informal relationships follow.

Firstly, the MEPs' conversations noted that NGOs or research institutes were more likely to take the initiative in approaching an MEP or political group on an issue, rather than individual researchers. They explained that while they had many different channels with experts and scholars given their experience and background, scholars may not be so inclined to reach out on their own, as reflected in other expert interviews (Guéguen & Vicky Marissen, 2022). They confirmed that think tanks and NGOs in Brussels seem to be the prime mediator with individual researchers in relation to the EP. At the same time, research institutes from the Member State country would also reach out to an MEP; for example, in the case of when one MEP took office, and rectors of universities would send a letter of congratulation and invite them to a meeting.

They also explained that if you have a very specific or niche expertise that not many academics or experts can speak to, an MEP might informally or formally reach out to a researcher they did not previously have a relationship with on a given topic. However, normally, informal contact with experts depends on the MEP's pre-established relationship with academia and researchers, and results in conversations held or advice informally solicited via calls, emails or discussions at events in Brussels. One of the MEP participants explained that as they had less familiarity with Brussels, they relied on the researcher contacts of a fellow, more seasoned MEP and their policy advisors. This underlines how personal contacts or networks play an important role.

A third point worth highlighting from one of the MEP discussions is the extent to which budget is pooled or used for research activities outside of formal channels depends on the MEP or the party. While it is not officially earmarked, an EP party may use budget to

commission studies informally, as well. For example, the Greens plan to commission a study on the human rights impact of the New Migration Pact in order to facilitate its implementation, as well as assist NGOs and practitioners in litigation. However, it should be stressed that it varies as to whether political groups and their MEPs decide to spend money on commissioning such research at all.

A final MEP participant remark is worth noting: they estimated that lobbying organizations took the initiative to reach out at least 80% of the time, while research institutes formed part of the other 20% of groups. This ratio somewhat parallels the composition of the Transparency Register in Figure 1. It remains an important takeaway in an overall examination of the research-policy nexus and corresponding dynamics in Brussels.

Policy Implications

Following this case study, while there is ample room for further comparative research and questions remain, some policy implications and reflections clearly emerge:

- 1. Transparency vs. Efficacy:** There does not seem to be the same rigor of transparency mechanisms in place for individual researchers as for registered organizations or interest groups, including NGOs and think tanks. MEPs are not required to provide an account of informal conversations held with individuals, and if their staff hold these conversations, accountability is even further removed. However, the question remains as to the extent this would really be necessary. EU institutions have already been criticized for bureaucratic management that can hamper effective science-based policymaking (Guéguen & Vicky Marissen, 2022). Moreover, stakeholder interviews noted how individual researchers seemed less likely to take initiative in the first place. Research and policy should further explore and address this question.
- 2. Improving available expertise for policymaking:** In order to better promote evidence-based policy drawing from a more diverse and comprehensive pool of experts beyond the “Brussels bubble,” researchers should be equipped to take the

initiative and disseminate their work. Independent research universities and institutions could offer individual researchers support in supplying the EP with their evidence in their research support structures. For example, institutional research support services could offer scientists tailored advice as to which parties and committees to target (given their research expertise), curate EU institution newsletters to follow, and keep researchers informed as to relevant MEPs and EU actors on social media for their field. As academia increasingly encourages demonstration of societal impact, supporting individual researchers in disseminating their research to the EP is key, beyond solely offering support in grant or funding solicitation (from EU institutions or other actors) and management. This might also assist in leveling the playing field with the activities of lobbying groups.

- 3. Further systematic research to understand informal network impact:** It would be important to map out how the different fields function in these informal circles and if there are differences in the relational process and agenda-setting. Here, migration in the Dutch context was the topic of the case study. But, does the discipline or issue matter? For example, such issues can be identified in formal mechanisms: in going over appraisals a parliamentary committee may ask for from the EPRS regarding European Commission impact assessments, with topics between 2019 and 2021 including the European Green Deal, the EU strategy on adaptation to climate change digital markets and digital services, artificial intelligence and corporate sustainability reporting, pay transparency (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022). How do Parliament party agendas and ideals relate to whether MEPs may be inclined to solicit evidence-based policies, and to what extent can informal interactions with researchers precede or instigate these formal routes? It would be useful to more systematically map out the informal modes of communication and exchange between individual academic experts and the EP, in order to understand dynamics of efficacy and expertise (or lack thereof).

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